

ACOUSTIC EMISSION FOR CYCLIC DAMAGE EVALUATION ON FIBERGLASS PIPES FABRICATED FOLLOWING RTP-1 METHODS AND SPECIFICATIONS.

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SUMMARY: Results from a series of cyclic tests performed on fiberglass pipes fabricated according to RTP-1 and Section X recommendations. The specimens were 20.32 cm (8 in) in internal diameter and 1.525 meters (5 feet) long. The construction layout consisted of an internal buildup for corrosion protection followed by a layer of continuous fiber winding. A state of pure hoop stress was imposed via an internal pressure system that allowed free axial movement of the pipe. This paper will present the results of the acoustic emission monitoring of these tests, and the relative effectiveness of AE in determining damage induced by cyclic loading.

KEYWORDS: acoustic emission, fatigue, nondestructive evaluation, pressure vessels.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials in general engineering structures are becoming popular in a variety of applications. One of the areas of interest is the fatigue or long term behavior of fiber composites. Current specifications allow for large variability in the fabrication of continuous winding tubular members. Consequently, properties of individual members built to the same design specifications and even within sections of the member itself will vary from each other. Reliable and precise estimation of material properties is very difficult at best, resulting in inaccuracies in the prediction models.

This variability in properties increases the need for reliable inspection methods for determining in situ conditions and reserve capacity of fiber composite structures. Because of the anisotropy and layered profile of composites, a method that monitors the global behavior of the material is best suited for this application. Acoustic emission is an inspection method

that monitors the global behavior of the structure. It is very adaptable to the environment conditions that exist around the structure inspected. It is also a nondestructive inspection method that in most cases allows the component or structure being inspected to remain in service.

Traditional parametric acoustic emission (AE) has been successfully applied in the monitoring of in service pressure vessels and railroad tank cars among other structures. This type of nondestructive evaluation is based on a statistical approach to damage assessment where, identification of damage mechanisms is not precise or reliable. The development of high fidelity broad band sensors and digital capturing equipment provide AE with a new methodology [1,2] based on mathematical wave propagation. This approach in addition to parametric AE will provide with a reliable tool that not only will identify the damage and its effect on the capacity but also the location where it happened.

The research program originated as a revision of test performed by A.B. Isham in the later 1960's [3]. Most of the design and fabrication criteria in the ASME codes is derived from the test results by Isham. Since the time of that program, materials and fabrication procedures have changed and improved. The objective is determining if the design values can be modified to reflect the improvements in the technology.

SPECIMEN DESCRIPTION

The specimens used in this program were glass fiber reinforced epoxy pipes made by the continuous winding process. Figure 1 shows the schematic of the layers in the specimens. The reinforcement was E-Glass with 60% content by volume and a winding angle of +/- 60 degrees in a vinyl-ester resin matrix. The content of fiber in the specimens was verified by chemically digesting the resin, with a deviation in the results of less than 5%.

Figure 1 Specimen description

Before testing, it was necessary to reinforce the end of the specimens, without it, failure will occur at the area of stress concentration produced by the seal plates. If failure occurs at this location, developing the correct relationship between strain, pressure and capacity will be difficult and not reliable. The reinforcement was designed with the use of elastic finite element analysis. During testing, it was found that the sensitivity to the difference between the specified dimensions or the reinforcement and those measured after fabrication was not considerable. The only restriction was that, the gradual reduction profile of thickness in the reinforcement must be similar to the one specified.

Figure 2 Leak detection system

In addition to the AE monitoring, strain records were kept of each specimen and a leak detector system was implemented. The leak detector is based on the CRIBBED™ monitoring system by Anderson Consulting [4]. Typically used to detect the deterioration of the corrosion barrier in pressure vessels, in this program, the system was implemented as means to detect cracking in the interior layers during fatigue testing. The system makes use of a electrically sensitive layer embedded in the thickness of the pipe. The layer is typically a Nexus veil. When cracking occurs, liquid from the inside of the pipe closed an electrical bridge to the Nexus layer and leakage is detected. Figure 2 shows and schematic of the leak detector setup and implementation in the test program.

The inside diameter of both sets was 20.32 cm (8 in) in internal diameter with a total length of and 1.525 meters (5 ft) each. To minimize the variability in fabrication typical in composite

materials, specimens were obtained from a single winding operation on a long mandrel. Each one of the longer pipes were 12.2 meters (40 ft) in length, in addition to the 1.525 meters (5 ft) specimens used; shorter sections were obtained at regular intervals for the fiber content tests. After reinforcement of the ends, the final test gage in each specimen was 0.61 meters (2 ft). Figure 3 shows a view of the specimen at the testing location.

The acoustic emission system used in the test program consisted of two separate units and sensor types. Both resonant to 150 kHz and high fidelity broad band sensors were used to acquire AE data. The data acquisition systems used was by Physical Acoustics Inc (PAC). These were the Transportation Instrument for the parametric information from resonant sensors and, the Mistras-2000 for the digital information.

Figure 3 Seal system internal pressure tests

TEST RESULTS

As it is expected on results from fatigue testing, and even more likely if associated with composite materials, the variability in behavior was considerable. Figure 4 shows the logarithmic plot of maximum strain to cycle life of the specimens tested.

Figure 4 Endurance plots for specimens tested

In the same figure, a trend line for the presented data points was calculated and plotted for reference. The equation used in the trend line is also shown in the figure inside a text box. All tests have consisted on an initial loading to the target pressure or strain while keeping AE records. After initial loading, pressure cycles between 344.74 kPa (50 psi) and the target pressure are induced. Regularly, the cycling is stopped for a slow loading to target pressure with AE records. The variability was evident even on the non-cycled tests, where the specimens were loaded to leakage monotonically. All damage mechanisms have been the same in the program. A single longitudinal crack, forms in the inside diameter of the

Figure 5 Typical failure surface

specimen followed by delamination in the winding portion and subsequent leakage. Figure 5 shows a view of the typical damaged section of the specimen.

As seen in the figure, the longitudinal crack extended through the corrosion barrier layer including the nexus layer for the leak detection system and formed a delamination at the interface between the barrier and the winding portion. None of the fiberglass specimens failed by burst and, additional loading was possible after leakage if, an interior liner was provided to the specimen. Leakage took place during the slow testing associated with the AE monitoring and has taken place at the last 2 min load hold at target pressure.

A comparison of the measured values during the static tests to the design ones obtained using RTP-1 specifications produce several interesting results. The design pressure of the specimen as built is 1378.95 kPa (200 psi) to leakage. Of all the specimens tested, the lowest leakage pressure obtained was 14.5 MPa (2100 psi). This is equivalent to a strength ratio of 13.5 at the continuous winding portion of the pipe.

ACOUSTIC EMISSION ANALYSIS

During the presentation of the AE results, references will be made to a first or primary AE knee and a secondary AE knee. The location of the knees is determined by comparing both the historic index (HI) of the AE records using the CARP procedure [5], along with the distribution of amplitudes plot and the signal strength curve calculated. The observed difference between the two defined knees consists in that the secondary knee took place at the pressure where significant AE during load holds was recorded. In some of the tests, there was no difference noted and only a single main knee was determined. This played an important role in the interpretation of the test results as it will be presented later. Figure 6 shows the plots with the utilized AE data associated with typical tests, where two separate knees were noticed.

In the figure, two clear maximum spikes are noticed in the historic index plot. A square box indicates the first spike and the second, by an elliptical one. In addition, considerable jumps in the signal strength plot are noticed and marked in the same way at the locations. Strictly speaking, it is expected that both plots, HI and signal strength, would show jumps at the same location since both are indicators of energy change in the AE records. However, the concentration of low amplitude events, as seen in the middle figure, at the second knee proves to be the difference between both spikes. Using the level of dB in the amplitudes in an attempt to identify the mechanism of damage would prove to be futile. However, the concentration of events, at this level, indicate a distributed damage progression in the system. Using both however, is a good way to determine if separate knees occur as defined in the previous paragraph. Figure 7 shows the estimated AE second knees for specimens tested under fatigue loading. At first glance it is apparent the inconsistency between the specimens as the result of fabrication variability. Even when some of these came from the same winding operation, their individual responses to applied pressure vary considerably. This variability in the response makes for a high level of uncertainty at the design phase.

Combining the records between the measured strains at the time the second AE knee was recorded and, the measured strains at the target pressure, a better consistency was noted in the results. Figure 8 shows a plot similar to the one in Figure 5, this one however measures the response as the difference between the measured strain at the second AE knee and the maximum strain in the specimen. A better grouping of the data is immediately noticed in the data. In addition, a clearer trend is noted at the highest levels of cyclic endurance. Indications

Figure 6 Determination of AE knee for typical test

of the possibility of an endurance limit for leakage capacity is noticed, and the error between the measured tests point and the averaging trend line is smaller. In the figure, the equation used for the determination of the trend line is presented in a text box. This equation is only valid for the specimens presented here, and no claims towards its applicability in design is made.

In general, we noted a good correlation between parametric AE data and the endurance of the specimens. Even when some specimens were tested at different rates, this does not appear to affect the results when normalized to the AE records. Prediction of life expectancy based on AE is feasible, even though additional supporting data is required to establish general guidelines that will apply to all combinations of winding to barrier. Parametric data however, did not appear to provide sufficient information for determining life expectancy of an already

Figure 7 Second AE knee pressure for fatigue specimens (kPa)

operating structure. No clear trends were noted in the data recorded during the cyclic testing of the specimens that would indicate imminent failure. The general tendency, for specimens with cycles larger than 1,000 was towards reduction of AE emissions at pressures lower than the target pressure. No significant event took place during the AE monitoring at the final cycle prior to failure for these specimens. Those that failed at less than 1,000 cycles showed a Felicity ratio [7,8] of less than 0.85 at the final loading. But this was not either consistent since some showed this ratio during the initial loading stages and not only at the final cycle. The scatter in the data, however, would indicate that or levels of the Felicity ratio of less than 0.85; failure is to be expected at very low levels of cycling. Therefore, during the first loading, stress levels should be kept below the point where the ratio becomes 0.85 or less. If this ratio is less than 0.85 for the pressure level of interest, it may be concluded that the vessel will not tolerate this level of stress during repeated use.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Results of cyclic tests at target pressures above 11,030 kPa (1600 psi) were relatively inconsistent, within common groups, as to the number of cycles required for failure or leakage. Strain measurements showed no clear loss of stiffness as the result of cycling. In addition, residual deformations recorded at the end of each static monitoring were mostly recovered in one day of rest. Tests performed at a target pressure of 8,272.8 kPa (1200 psi) lasted for a total of one million cycles before being tested to leakage. The results indicated that little or no reduction in the capacity was recorded after the cycles.

Acoustic emission during first loading of the specimens indicates that prediction of life endurance based on this NDE technique is possible. The plot in Figure 8 shows that there is a correlation between the 2nd AE knee stress and the expected life to leakage of the specimen in tests between zero and target pressure. The lowest pressure where this second AE knee was recorded was 5515.2 kPa (800 psi); the results of the cyclic test suggest that this could be the endurance limit of the specimens. Following the results of tests at 8,272.8 kPa (1200 psi) of pressure span, we noted that these specimens had the second knee recorded at 7,583.4 kPa

Figure 8 Endurance plot with AE knee consideration

(1100 psi), slightly lower than the maximum pressure. Using this AE milestone as the endurance limit, we can see that allowable strains of up to 0.3% or more may be possible in the design of vessels in the direction of the loading. This would result in an improvement of up to 300% over the previously accepted limit.

Acoustic emission, however, in its parametric form does not appear to present any indication during the cyclic phase that would help in the prediction of remaining life. The general tendency of the specimen was to reduce the amount of emission at pressures lower than the target pressure as the number of cycles increased. In the cases of specimens at pressures above 11,030 kPa (1600 psi), at the time of leakage, the Felicity ratio was 0.85 or lower. This does not apply to the specimens tested at target pressures under 11,030 kPa (1600 psi) where, after a number of cycles, no clear acoustic emission is noted until the target pressure is reached. A possibility of predicting remaining life is apparent in these cases but only if the complete load history of the specimen is known beforehand. In real structures, this is extremely difficult to accurately obtain unless is predisposed that way from the beginning of the service life of the structure.

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